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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Yangi O'zbekistonning mintaqaviy va global geosiyosiy pozitsiyasi: milliy o'zlik va media reprezentatsiya tahlili	16
Salim Doniyorov	
Axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari vositasida o'quvchilarning adabiy tahlil kompetensiyasini shakllantirish	21
Djo'rayev Yorqin Xolnizozovich, Xoldarova Gulchehra Tajibayevna	
Adabiy tahlil kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda elektron darsliklar va multimedia vositalaridan foydalanish.....	26
Djo'rayev Yorqin Xolnizozovich	
Ta'limdagi hurfikrlikni rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	29
Yunusov Dilshod Raxmatovich	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarda tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	32
Aliqulova Habiba Bahranovna	
Ayollar boksida jismoniy tayyorgarlikning yosh qizlar salomatligiga ta'siri	36
Majidov Ruslan Rustam o'g'li, Komilova Ismigul O'ktamjon qizi	
Talaba-yoshlarda internet risklarning oldini olishning pedagogik modeli	41
Muradova Maftuna Komilovna, Mamadaliyeva Umida Isroiljonovna	
Диагностика креативности студентов педагогических вузов в процессе изучения специальных дисциплин.....	44
Уразова Марина Батыровна, Соибова Толифа Дилмуродовна	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kommunikativ kompetentlikni shakllantirishning metodik xususiyatlari.....	49
Tashibekova Munajat Xoshimovna	
Mariya Montessori ta'limida bolalarning mustaqilligini va ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-didaktik shart-sharoitlari.....	53
Asqarova Ma'mura Sadriddinovna	
O'spirinlik yoshida namoyon bo'ladigan agressiv xulqning psixologik xususiyati	59
Atajanova Xurjon Pirnazar qizi	
O'zbekiston jurnalistikasining rivojlanishida jadidlarning o'rni: jurnalistikada yangi trend	64
Murtozayeva Nigora Murtoza qizi	
Virtual ta'lim texnologiyasining ta'lim jarayonini takomillashtirishdagi ahamiyati.....	67
Muxsiyeva Aziza Shamsitdinovna	
Kelajakdagi o'qituvchilarning pedagogik kreativligini ta'limiy o'yinlar orqali rivojlantirish yo'llari	69
N. A. Musayeva	
Talabalarda lisoniy tafakkurni shakllantirishga psixolingvistik yondashuvning didaktik tamoyillari	76
Odijonova Kamola Abduvosit qizi	
Strategies for Overcoming Difficulties in Using Authentic Materials in English Language Teaching	81
Qosimov Jaloliddin Abduvali o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	84
Qurbonova Buzaynab Nurmuxammadiyevna	
Inspektor-psixologlarda ijtimoiy-psixologik kompetentlikning kasbiy faoliyatdagi ahamiyati	87
Raxmanova Dilnoza Farmanovna	
Qo'ng'iro't tumani toponimlarining leksik-semantik va genetik xususiyatlari	90
Shamshaddinova Saodat Saparbayevna	
Variativ yondashuv asosida 5–9-sinf o'quvchilarida valeologik madaniyatni rivojlantirishning didaktik modeli va metodik ta'minoti	93
Shamuratov Asqar Abdullayevich	

The Structural Composition and Developmental Stages of Critical Thinking Skills.....	98
<i>Shuxratjon Ismoiljonov Boymirza o'g'li</i>	
Yosh rahbar kadrlarni lavozimlarga tayinlashning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	106
<i>Sobitov Otabek</i>	
O'zbekistonda erta turmush qurish masalasi va uning psixologik tahlillari.....	111
<i>Sodiqova Gulbarno Odiljon qizi</i>	
Adaptiv sportning inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida alohida ta'limga ehtiyoji bo'lgan o'quvchilarning jismoniy va funksional rivojlanishidagi ahamiyati.....	114
<i>Xasanova Sarvinov To'liqinjon qizi</i>	
Yosh futbolchilarda texnik mahoratni rivojlantirishda differentsiallashgan mashg'ulotlar modelini qo'llash samaradorligi	118
<i>Zayniddinov Tojiddin Baxriddinovich</i>	
Фразеологизмы как носители культуры: проблемы перевода и методы обучения	123
<i>Хамидова Гулноза Турсунбой кизи</i>	
Talabalarni kreativ yondashuv asosida tarbiyaviy–innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlash jarayonlari.....	127
<i>Adizova G. M.</i>	
Iqtidorli bolalarni psixologik-pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash	131
<i>Ismoilova Adolat Anvarovna</i>	
STEAM – ta'lim texnologiyasi asosida o'quvchilarning fazoviy tasavvurlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	134
<i>So'fiboyeva Gulchehra Mamurjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy ko'nikmalar va kompetentlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	138
<i>Fayzullayeva Xovoxon Xayrullo qizi</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'limga muhtoj bolalar bilan ishlashda tarbiyachining roli.....	142
<i>Mansurova Lobar Luqmon qizi, Boqiyeva E'zoza Mashrab qizi</i>	
Rivojlanishida nuqsoni bor bolalarni ta'lim-tarbiyalashning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	146
<i>Tojiboyeva Osiyoxon Alisher qizi</i>	
Xalqaro ta'lim tashkilotlari faoliyatining nazariy asoslari.....	150
<i>Abdusamadova Aziza Kamoliddin qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni ijtimoiy texnologiyalar asosida ijtimoiy-pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash tizimi sifatida.....	153
<i>Shanazarov Otabek</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda STEAM yondashuvini loyiha asosida joriy etishning pedagogik strategiyalari	158
<i>Radjapova Zuxra Tirkashevna, Abdullayeva Sarviniso</i>	
Matematika ta'limida modellashtirishning psixologik va metodik asoslari: disum loyihasi tahlili.....	161
<i>Xaydarov Xurshid Ismatovich</i>	
Darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda gandbolchilarning tezkorligini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	166
<i>Ismatullayeva Zuhra Rustam qizi</i>	
Osiyo xalq o'yinlari asosida jismoniy tarbiya jarayonini samarali tashkil etishning pedagogik shartlari	170
<i>Abdullayev Yashnarjon Mahkamovich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning innovatsion kompetentligini shakllantirishda klasterli ta'lim muhitining imkoniyatlari.....	173
<i>Abduraxmanov M. B.</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida tanqidiy fikrlash.....	178
<i>Chinaliyeva Ayjamal Baxitjanovna</i>	
Talabalarda raqamli ta'lim madaniyatini rivojlantirish.....	181
<i>Eshqurbonova Nafisa Bahodir qizi</i>	
Blended Educational Technologies in Higher Education: A Systematic Analysis of Foreign Research.....	183
<i>Fozilova Maxina Adashevna</i>	
Voyaga yetmaganlarda deviant xulq shakllanishida ijtimoiy-psixologik omillarning roli.....	188
<i>Galdiyeva Mehribon Durdiyevna, Saydazimov Alisher Nurali o'g'li</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

Boshlang'ich tayyorlov guruhida ulotqirish texnikasi elementlarini o'rgatish samaradorligi.....	191
Hayitmurodova Nasiba Abdusalimovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida tarbiya fanini o'qitishning metodik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish zaruriyati.....	197
Inoyatova Zulfiya Xamdamovna	
Talabalarni ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatiga jalb etishning metodologik asoslari.....	199
Karimova Madinabonu Dilshodbek qizi	
Kompetentligini baholash mezonlari va indikatorlarini ishlab chiqish	203
Kayumov Oybek Achilovich	
Kasbiy refleksiya asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogik mahoratini rivojlantirish.....	209
Miraxmedova Mubina Mirxalil qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.....	211
Nisanbayeva Akmaral Kaldibayevna	
Maxsus ta'lim dasturlari orqali iqtidorli talabalarining ijodiy salohiyatini rivojlantirish	214
Rayimova Shahlo Sobirjon qizi	
STEAM ta'limida ijtimoiy intellektni rivojlantirish metodlari	217
Toshev Elbek Choriyevich	
Innovatsion texnologiyalar va ularning tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarini tayyorlash tizimidagi roli.....	223
Usmanov Botir Allaberdievich	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning ijtimoiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda volontyorlik faoliyatining ahamiyati.....	227
Xalilova Dilnoza Furkatovna	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda robototexnikaning ahamiyati va o'rni	230
Xodiyeva Dilrabo Pirimovna	
Working With Visual AIDS in Teaching English in Primary Education	233
Yunusova Nodira Akhmadjanovna	
Teatr texnologiyalarini maktabgacha ta'limga integratsiya qilishning pedagogik shartlari	237
Abdullayeva Aziza Abdurazzoq qizi, Salimova Dilmira Farxodovna	

WORKING WITH VISUAL AIDS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This research examines the use of visual aids in teaching English to primary school children, integrating theoretical frameworks with practical classroom applications. Visual aids such as photos, flashcards, videos, and realia help students better understand and retain new vocabulary. The study analyzes the role of visual aids in enhancing motivation, creativity, and linguistic accuracy. The research was conducted at a primary school in the Tashkent region with the participation of 40 students aged 8-10. Classroom observations and teacher interviews were used to collect both qualitative and quantitative data. The findings indicate that the use of visual aids significantly improved students' engagement and learning outcomes. The study concludes that the integration of visual elements is essential for effective and engaging English language teaching in primary education.

Key words: visual aids, primary education, language acquisition, motivation, comprehension, teaching methods, EFL classes.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tili darslarida vizual vositalardan foydalanish samaradorligini nazariy va amaliy jihatdan o'rganadi. Rasmlar, fleshkartlar, videolar va real obyektlardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning yangi so'zlarni anglash va eslab qolish jarayonini osonlashtiradi. Tadqiqotda vizual vositalarning o'quvchilar motivatsiyasi, ijodkorligi va nutq aniqligiga ta'siri tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot Toshkent viloyatidagi boshlang'ich maktabda 8-10 yoshli 40 nafar o'quvchi ishtirokida olib borildi. Ma'lumotlar sinf kuzatuv va o'qituvchilar bilan suhbatlar asosida yig'ildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, vizual vositalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning faolligi va o'zlashtirish ko'rsatkichlarini sezilarli darajada yaxshiladi. Tadqiqot yakunida ingliz tili ta'limida vizual materiallardan foydalanish samarali o'qitishning muhim omili ekanligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: vizual vositalar, boshlang'ich ta'lim, til o'rganish, motivatsiya, tushunish, o'qitish strategiyalari, ingliz tili darsi.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматривается использование наглядных пособий при обучении английскому языку в начальных классах с интеграцией теоретических и практических аспектов. Использование изображений, карточек, видео и реальных предметов способствует лучшему пониманию и запоминанию новых слов. Исследование проведено в начальной школе Ташкентской области с участием 40 учеников в возрасте 8-10 лет. Данные были собраны с помощью наблюдений и интервью с учителями. Результаты показали, что визуальные средства значительно повышают мотивацию, активность и успеваемость учащихся. В заключение подчеркивается, что интеграция визуальных материалов является ключевым фактором эффективного преподавания английского языка в начальной школе.

Ключевые слова: наглядные пособия, начальное образование, изучение языка, мотивация, понимание, методика преподавания, EFL-классы.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching English to young learners requires innovative approaches that foster engagement and facilitate learning. Visual aids are among the most effective instructional tools, as they help maintain students' interest and enhance comprehension (Harmer, 2015, p. 64). Due to their developmental stage, primary school students learn best when linguistic input is clear, vivid, and supported by visual elements.

According to Paivio's Dual Coding Theory (1986, p. 55), the brain processes information through both verbal and visual channels, thereby improving memory and recall. Therefore, the use of visual aids in English classes enables learners to associate linguistic concepts with meaningful images. The National Curriculum for Foreign Languages (2021) in Uzbekistan emphasizes communicative competence and the use of interactive materials in language instruction. However, many teachers still rely on traditional approaches focused

mainly on memorization and textbook-based activities, which creates a gap between theoretical frameworks and classroom practice (Usmonova, 2020, p. 89).

Consequently, investigating the role of visual aids in enhancing primary-level English instruction is both timely and significant. This study aims to assess the effectiveness of visual aids in teaching vocabulary and grammar to young learners, explore teachers' and students' attitudes toward the use of visual aids in English lessons, and provide practical recommendations for integrating visual aids into primary English classrooms. Overall, this research seeks to enhance understanding of how visual materials contribute to motivation, comprehension, and long-term language retention among primary school students by combining theoretical insights with empirical classroom data.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of visual aids in education is grounded in cognitive and constructivist learning theories. Piaget (1952, p. 41) emphasized that children acquire knowledge through active interaction with their environment, while Vygotsky (1978, p. 86) argued that social interaction and scaffolding support the development of higher-order thinking skills. When visual materials such as images, charts, and videos are used, they function as scaffolds that facilitate language comprehension within the learner's zone of proximal development (ZPD). Mayer's (2009, p. 63) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning suggests that students learn more effectively when information is presented simultaneously through visual and auditory channels, as this dual representation reduces cognitive load and enhances retention.

Bruner (1996, p. 78) also noted that visual representation is particularly beneficial for young learners who rely heavily on sensory experiences. Numerous studies confirm that the use of visual aids in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms is highly effective. Wright (2010, p. 57) found that images stimulate learners' creativity and contextual understanding, while Dörnyei and Ushioda (2013, p. 112) demonstrated that visual stimuli enhance motivation by making lessons more engaging and emotionally meaningful.

Harmer (2015, p. 65) stated that the use of images, flashcards, and realia promotes active participation, especially in vocabulary and speaking activities. Arslan and Saka (2021, p. 22) found that visual-based instruction improved elementary students' vocabulary retention and pronunciation accuracy, and visual aids also enable teachers to address diverse proficiency levels within the same classroom (Richards & Rodgers, 2014, p. 88). Karimova (2022, p. 49) reported that in Uzbekistan, visual aids increase student participation and cultural awareness in English lessons, and these findings align with global research indicating that visual tools not only enhance comprehension but also foster positive attitudes toward language learning (Alqahtani, 2018, p. 103).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods to examine the impact of visual aids on English learning outcomes among primary school students. The study was conducted in a public primary school in the Tashkent region during the 2025-2026 academic year, involving 40 students aged 8-10. The participants were randomly divided into two groups: an experimental group with 20 students and a control group with 20 students, both of which were comparable in age and initial English proficiency.

The experimental group received instruction with visual aids, whereas the control group was taught using traditional textbook-based methods. Data were collected using multiple instruments, including pre-tests and post-tests to measure vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension before and after the intervention, classroom observations to assess engagement, motivation, and attention, as well as teacher interviews to gain insights into classroom practices and the perceived effectiveness of visual aids. The intervention lasted four weeks, with three English lessons per week, and the experimental group's lessons incorporated various visual aids such as flashcards, videos, posters, and realia to support vocabulary acquisition and sentence structure learning.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Descriptive statistics were used to calculate mean scores for pre- and post-tests and percentage gains in vocabulary and comprehension for both groups, while thematic analysis was applied to qualitative data from teacher interviews to identify recurring themes related to engagement, motivation, and classroom challenges. This mixed-methods approach provided a comprehensive understanding of the impact of visual aids on both academic performance and the overall classroom environment. Quantitative Findings.

Table 1: Comparison of Vocabulary Test Scores (Pre-test and Post-test)

Group	Pre-test Mean (%)	Post-test Mean (%)	Improvement (%)
Experimental (Visual Aids)	58.4	86.2	27.8
Control (Traditional)	59.1	70.3	11.2

The findings show that the experimental group, which used visual aids, performed 27.8% better on the vocabulary test compared to the control group, which showed an improvement of only 11.2%. This study supports Mayer's (2009, p. 63) assertion that the combination of visual and verbal elements enhances knowledge retention. It also aligns with the findings of Arslan and Saka (2021, p. 22), which indicate that young learners exposed to visual materials demonstrate significant vocabulary improvement. **Qualitative Findings**

Table 2: Summary of Teacher Interview Themes

Theme	Description	Example Quotation
Increased Motivation	Students were more enthusiastic and focused when visuals were used.	"Children pay more attention when I show colourful pictures or short videos."
Better Comprehension	Visuals helped clarify new words and grammar patterns.	"They understand meanings faster through images rather than long explanations."
Classroom Interaction	Visual aids encouraged group work and oral participation.	"Students love describing pictures together – it improves their speaking confidence."
Challenges	Some visuals required preparation time or technology.	"It's sometimes hard to find appropriate images for every topic."

The interviews showed that instructors observed higher engagement, improved comprehension, and better interaction when visual aids were employed. However, they also highlighted several practical challenges, including limited time and restricted access to multimedia materials. These results indicate that visual aids can significantly enhance student learning, but instructors require institutional support and digital resources to implement them effectively (Richards & Rodgers, 2014, p. 89).

The findings demonstrate that visual aids substantially improve primary school students' ability to retain terminology, maintain motivation, and actively participate in class. These results are consistent with Paivio's (1986) Dual Coding Theory and Mayer's (2009) Multimedia Learning Theory, both of which emphasise the importance of integrating verbal and visual information to enhance learning outcomes. Visually supported classes created a more engaging and effective learning environment compared to conventional lessons. This aligns with Zoltán Dörnyei and Ema Ushioda (2013, p. 112), who emphasized that emotionally engaging stimuli, including images and videos, enhance intrinsic motivation. Teacher feedback also indicated that images support students who are shy or have limited communication skills, which is consistent with Lev Vygotsky (1978, p. 87), who highlighted social interaction as a key mechanism of learning.

However, several challenges were identified, including insufficient technological resources, inadequate training, and limited preparation time. These findings correspond with Karimova (2022, p. 51), who observed that instructors in Uzbek classrooms often lack the necessary digital tools to facilitate more interactive learning. Addressing these issues through professional development and improved school infrastructure could significantly enhance the effectiveness of visual-based English instruction.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that visual aids are highly effective in teaching English to young learners. Incorporating visual elements into lessons improves comprehension, increases engagement, and encourages active participation, ultimately leading to measurable improvements in academic performance. Both theoretical and empirical evidence support the idea that visual materials help bridge the gap between abstract linguistic concepts and concrete learner understanding.

Teachers are encouraged to integrate a wide range of visual aids—such as flashcards, realia, digital images, and videos—to enhance both engagement and instructional effectiveness. Policymakers and educational institutions should ensure that teachers are provided with adequate resources and training to support sustainable implementation of visual-based teaching approaches.

Future research may explore the long-term effects of visual learning and examine the potential of emerging digital technologies, such as interactive whiteboards and augmented reality, in further enhancing language development among young learners.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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